

April 20, 2022

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. Shang Shane Pinto, a student of Srinivas University, College of hotel Management and Tourism, Managalore has undergone Industrial Training with us from December 13, 2021 to April 18, 2022 in Front Office, Housekeeping, Food & Beverage Service and Culinary departments.

During the tenure of his training we found him to be sincere and hardworking.

We sincerely wish him success in all his future endeavors.

For Grand Hyatt Goa

Siddhi Sardessai
Assistant Personnel Manager

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